

SOME PROBLEMS OF UNDERSTANDING THE ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL STATUS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES AND THEIR EMPLOYEES ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE NATIONAL GUARD OF UKRAINE*Shmilo N.**PhD student at the West Ukrainian National University**ORCID: 0009-0009-4639-6526***Abstract**

The article is devoted to the study of the essence of administrative and legal status, as well as the concept and characteristics of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency and its employee. The author identifies the problems in determining the constituent elements of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency, and also examines the main views of scholars on this issue. Having examined the views of individual theorists in the field of administrative law, it should be noted that we believe that in a simplified sense, administrative and legal status should be understood as a set of rights and obligations provided for by administrative law and assigned to a specific entity. At the same time, the understanding of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency has its own peculiarities. Analyzing the administrative and legal status of law enforcement officers, the author concludes that such subjects combine three different statuses: the general status of a citizen of Ukraine; special status determined by special laws which establish the organizational and legal framework for the activities of a law enforcement agency; and, of course, when a law enforcement officer holds a certain position within a law enforcement agency, the status determined by the position is also imposed on the general administrative and legal status. It is stated that the National Guard of Ukraine performs its functions in a specific area of administrative and legal relations relating to law enforcement. These relations arise in the course of application of administrative coercion measures and in cases of violation of law, including administrative offenses. The National Guard of Ukraine is an integral part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, which is responsible for public administration in the field of internal affairs. The author supports the current approach that exists in the state to consider the function of state bodies, including law enforcement agencies, through the prism of public services. The author emphasizes that it is necessary to distinguish between the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency and the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement officer, since the concepts of administrative and legal status of a body or its subdivision and administrative and legal status of officials of these bodies cannot be equated. Based on the analysis of the issue under study, the author suggests the ways to improve the administrative and legal status of law enforcement officers.

Keywords: legal status, law enforcement agency, law enforcement officer, administrative and legal status.

Introduction. The problem of the essence of the concepts of "law enforcement agency" and "law enforcement officer" is quite complex and requires active actions on the part of the legislator, which will consist in amending the legal framework and harmonizing these concepts with each other. This includes the part of public authorities' officials who have to interpret these provisions and put them into practice. Another problem is that it requires harmonization of many aspects, including not only functions and responsibilities, but also regulatory regulation, relations with citizens, interaction with other government agencies, as well as ethics and responsibility.

From the perspective of the practical activities of law enforcement agencies in Ukraine, the definition of "law enforcement agency" depends on defining the limits of competence and powers of law enforcement officers, as well as ensuring that their activities respect human rights and civil liberties. There needs to be a constant balance between protecting civilian security and ensuring their rights and freedoms. In this context, it is advisable to study the concept of "administrative and legal status" as well as "administrative and legal status of a law enforcement officer". Moreover, under martial law, even more responsibilities are assigned to law enforcement agencies, which may include both internal security and the participation of individual employees in repelling armed aggression.

Analysis of scientific publications. Both domestic and foreign scholars have studied the issue of the administrative and legal status of law enforcement agencies and law enforcement officers, including: Kolomojts T.O., Liakhovych U.I., Lebid N.V., Bytyak Y.P., Bandurka O.O., Bryhinets O.O., Bezpalova O.I., Katrych D.K., Horbach D.O. and others. Despite this, some issues remain open and require scientific research.

The aim of the work. The purpose of the proposed research is a complete and comprehensive study and analysis of the administrative and legal status of law enforcement agencies and their employees, carried out on the basis of the National Guard of Ukraine.

Review and discussion. When studying the concept of "administrative and legal status", we paid attention to the works of N. M. Onishchenko and O. V. Zaychuk, who argue that legal status is a system of rights, freedoms, legitimate interests and obligations of a subject of public relations which are enshrined and guaranteed by the State under the law. They believe that the characteristic features of legal status are: 1) universality (which applies to all subjects); 2) individuality (which reflects the personal characteristics of a person and his/her real position in social relations); 3) interconnection with other components;

4) systematic nature [1, P. 366]. According to T.A. Kolomojts, administrative and legal status is a set of

rights and obligations determined by the rules of administrative law for a particular body. At the same time, a key aspect of the subject's acquisition of administrative and legal status is the availability of specific rights and obligations that are reproduced both within and outside of administrative legal relations [2, P. 64]. U. I. Liakhovych, a scientist in the field of administrative law, considers legal status as a complex legal concept that determines the legal position of any subject in society and the state. This concept guarantees the realization and protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of participants to legal relations [3]. In turn, V. Averyanov proposed a different understanding of the concept of administrative and legal status. Thus, in his opinion, a set of subjective rights and obligations that are specifically assigned to a particular subject and provided for by administrative and legal norms is called administrative and legal status. He also identified specific features on which the acquisition of administrative and legal status depends. The scientist included: the existence of administrative rights and obligations that a person can exercise; consolidation of such rights and obligations by the rules of law; characterizing the peculiarities of such a subject's position.

Having examined the views of individual theorists in the field of administrative law, it is worth noting that we believe that in a simplified sense, administrative and legal status should be understood as a set of rights and obligations provided for by administrative law and assigned to a particular subject.

At the same time, the understanding of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency has its own peculiarities. Thus, N.V. Lebid points out that the legal status of a state body consists of four main elements: the target block, competence, organizational block and responsibility. The target block takes into account such aspects as "purpose", "tasks" and "functions" [4, P. 39-40]. S.V. Kivalov, expressing his opinion on the administrative and legal status of central executive bodies, describes it by means of their inherent functions, tasks and competence [5, P. 96-99]. In his research on the administrative and legal status of civil servants, scholar Y. P. Bytyak points out that the status of a position is determined by its establishment and determines the official position of an employee. It stipulates the requirements for a candidate for a position, conveys the essence and content of public service relations and is a set of rules for civil service - rights, duties, restrictions, prohibitions, guarantees, social protection and responsibility [6, P. 28]. In turn, O.O. Bandurka believes that the legal status of a public authority is the total scope of its legal powers, the exercise of which guarantees the implementation of its tasks [7, P. 23].

As a result of the study of the views of various scholars on the main components of the administrative and legal status of a public authority, we can conclude and agree with O. Bryginty, who believes that the most common approach is that the administrative and legal status of a public authority consists of the following elements:

1. Targeted, including the principles, goals, objectives and functions of the public authority.
2. Structural and organizational, which regulates

the procedure for establishment, reorganization, liquidation, operating procedures, the right to official symbols, and linear and functional subordination.

3. Competent, which includes a set of powers related to:

a) rights and obligations related to the exercise of power, participation in management relations, and the right to issue certain acts.

b) subordination, legal consolidation of objects, subjects and affairs covered by the authority [8, P. 172].

When analyzing the administrative and legal status of law enforcement officers, it should be noted that such subjects combine three different statuses: the general status of a citizen of Ukraine; a special status determined by special laws that establish the organizational and legal framework for the activities of a law enforcement agency; and, of course, when a law enforcement officer holds a certain position within a law enforcement agency, the status determined by the position is also imposed on the general administrative and legal status. Thus, for the purpose of a complete and comprehensive analysis of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement officer, it is necessary to analyze these components. Let us try to carry out such an analysis on the example of such a law enforcement agency as the National Guard of Ukraine.

The National Guard of Ukraine performs its functions in a specific sphere of administrative and legal relations related to law enforcement. These relations arise in the process of applying administrative coercion measures and in cases of violation of the law, including administrative offenses. The National Guard of Ukraine is an integral part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, which is responsible for public administration in the field of internal affairs. The main purpose of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, protection of property, the constitutional order of Ukraine, as well as prevention of offenses and ensuring the country's defense capability [9].

According to Art. 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On the National Guard", the National Guard of Ukraine is a military formation that performs law enforcement functions. It is an integral part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine and is tasked with protecting the lives, rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, society and the state from criminal and other unlawful interference, ensuring public safety and order, and cooperating with law enforcement agencies to ensure state security and protect the state border. It also combats terrorist activities, illegal paramilitary or armed groups, terrorist organizations, organized criminal groups and other criminal organizations [10].

Having defined the concept of the National Guard of Ukraine and its tasks, it is advisable to define its functions. The word "function" (translated from Latin as "fulfillment") is a concept of the systems approach that can be used to describe any system, including social, technical, biological and other systems. The main purpose of using this category in all cases is to define the standard activities of the system, the description of which allows the system to achieve its goal [11, P. 54]. According to L.V. Koval, the functions of a state body

are the main aspects of its activities, which are reflected in the defined tasks of the body to meet the important needs of the managed object. These functions are realized through the actions of structural subdivisions (and officials) of the body which perform the powers assigned to them [12, P. 64]. In turn, V.B. Averyanov points out that the function of an executive body can be described as a generalized characteristic of the purpose and direction of its actions aimed at achieving specific goals and objectives of public administration. Understanding these functions allows us to clearly distinguish them from the scope of powers and mode of action of the executive body and its officials [13].

At the same time, the approach that exists in the state to consider the function of state bodies, including law enforcement agencies, through the prism of public services is quite relevant. In the broadest sense, public services are defined as outputs provided to users by public authorities to fulfill their obligations to the citizens of the country [14]. This broad approach allows for the inclusion of a variety of actions by public authorities, from budgeting to the provision of state pensions. In this context, an "output" or "service" refers to the result of the work of a public authority, which can be tangible or informational, such as a budget, statistical report or issuance of documents. In a narrower sense, a public service is defined as a way of ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens and organizations, which is normatively established and implemented through the interaction of individuals or legal entities with state bodies or employees [15]. In addition, for example, there is a widespread position that the National Police is a service agency and provides services in the following areas: "ensuring public safety and order; protection of human rights and freedoms, as well as the interests of society and the state; combating crime; providing, within the limits established by law, services to assist persons who, for personal, economic, social reasons or as a result of emergencies, need such assistance" [10]. We believe that this position is appropriate and should be applied to all law enforcement agencies, including the National Guard of Ukraine.

They are defined by the relevant law. For example, according to Article 2 of the Law of Ukraine "On the National Guard", it is vested with the following functions: "protection of the constitutional order of Ukraine, the integrity of its territory from attempts to change them by force; protection of public safety and order, ensuring protection and safeguarding of life, health, rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens; participation in ensuring public safety and protection of public safety and order during meetings, rallies, marches, demonstrations and other mass events that pose a danger to the life and health of citizens; ensuring protection of public authorities, the list of which is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine

We believe that this list of functions should be classified. The classification of law enforcement functions was discussed by Y.O. Zahumenna. Thus, she distinguishes law enforcement functions of the state into main and auxiliary functions. The main law enforcement function includes the following types:

preventive; protective; security; operational and investigative; investigation of crimes; court proceedings; consideration of cases on administrative offenses; consideration of cases on financial and administrative and economic offenses; execution of sentences, decisions, rulings and resolutions of courts, decisions of pre-trial investigation bodies and prosecutors; resocialization. The auxiliary law enforcement functions include the following: control (supervisory); permitting; rulemaking; law-explaining; analytical; informational; coordination [16, P. 66].

As for the functions of the National Guard of Ukraine, in our opinion, they were quite accurately listed by Horbach D.O. Thus, he believes that all the functions listed above should be grouped into lawmaking, executive and administrative, and purely law enforcement [17].

At the same time, it should be emphasized that it is necessary to distinguish between the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency and the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement officer. As correctly pointed out by D.K. Katrych, the concepts of administrative and legal status of a body or its subdivision and administrative and legal status of officials of these bodies cannot be equated [18, P. 32]. The characterization of the legal status of the National Guard involves not only the power within the organization, but also the ability to act on behalf of the State in the performance of public order and security functions. The second aspect is the established restrictions and requirements concerning both entering the civil service and performing it.

The availability of guarantees of social and legal protection is another important component of the administrative and legal status of the National Guard. In addition, it should be noted the increased responsibility of persons serving in the National Guard of Ukraine both for their actions during service and for events occurring outside the service [19, P. 43].

The peculiarities of the administrative and legal status of the National Guard include the fact that they have not only general rights and obligations defined by the Constitution of Ukraine and the Law of Ukraine "On the National Police", but also rights and obligations arising from the position they hold in the police. Thus, the administrative and legal status of a person serving in the National Guard can be viewed in two aspects:

- elements inherent in a particular position (job rights and duties, responsibilities, etc.). These aspects are determined during the appointment to a particular position in the staffing table of the National Guard and are enshrined in job descriptions, staffing tables, etc. When filling a position, they become elements of the legal status of a particular official;

- elements that are not tied to a specific position (e.g., general rights and obligations, restrictions and prohibitions, liability) that apply to all civil servants and all members of the National Guard. These aspects are contained in the Law of Ukraine "On the National Guard".

The structure of the administrative and legal status of the National Guard includes: rights and duties; restrictions and prohibitions related to service in the police; guarantees of professional activity [19, P. 44].

Having analyzed the constituent elements of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency and its employee, it should be emphasized that the lack of a unified and uniform understanding of the concepts is a rather problematic issue that affects the effectiveness of law enforcement activities. In addition, the administrative and legal status of law enforcement agencies of Ukraine and their employees needs to be improved, in particular in the following areas: improving professional competence, which will include expanding training programs and introducing a system of continuous professional training for law enforcement officers of various law enforcement agencies to promote their professional development and improve the quality of performance of their duties; ensuring human and civil rights, in particular, strengthening measures to protect and ensure human rights

These measures, together with others, can help improve the administrative and legal status of law enforcement agencies and ensure effective and honest law enforcement.

Conclusions. The concepts of the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency of Ukraine and its employee are not the same in content, and at the same time they are difficult to understand and multifaceted for evaluation and analysis. For their proper understanding, it is necessary to analyze and identify the components of such status. The administrative and legal status of a law enforcement officer includes 3 aspects: target, structural and organizational, and competence. It is also worth noting that within the administrative and legal status of a law enforcement agency, it would be advisable to introduce the concept of "public service" along with functions.

References

1. Theory of State and Law. Academic course: textbook / O. V. Zaychuk, N. M. Onishchenko - Kyiv: Yurinkom Inter, 2008. 688 p. [in Ukrainian].
2. Kolomoyets T. O. Administrative law of Ukraine. Academic course: textbook. Kyiv, 2011. p. 284. [in Ukrainian].
3. Liakhovych UI Organizational and legal support for the implementation of the administrative and legal status of a civil servant: dissertation ... Candidate of Law: specialty 12.00.07 / Ulyana Ivanovna Liakhovych. - K., 2008 // [Electronic resource] - Access mode: [http:// adminpravo.com.ua](http://adminpravo.com.ua). [in Ukrainian].
4. Lebid N.V. Administrative and legal status of state inspections in Ukraine: Candidate of Law degree: 12.00.07 / N.V. Lebid; National University of Internal Affairs. - Kh., 2004. 202 p. [in Ukrainian].
5. Administrative law of Ukraine: textbook / under the general editorship of S.V. Kivalov. Kharkiv, 2004. 268. [in Ukrainian].
6. Bytyak Y. P. Civil service in Ukraine: problems of formation, development and functioning: PhD thesis ... Doctor of Law: 12.00.07. Kharkiv, 2006. 38 c. [in Ukrainian].

7. Bandurka O.O. State Tax Service in Ukraine: system, legal status, modernization. Kharkiv: Publishing house of the National University of Internal Affairs. 2004. 234 c. [in Ukrainian].

8. Bryhinets O.O. Administrative and legal status of the State Tax Service of Ukraine: Candidate of Law degree: 12.00.07 / Bryhinets Oleksandr Oleksiyovych. Irpin, 2011. 220 c.

9. Bezpalova O. I., Horbach D. O. Concept and structure of the administrative and legal status of the National Guard of Ukraine. Internet resource. URL: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefind-mkaj/https://dspace.univd.edu.ua/server/api/core/bitstreams/020f51b1-5359-45aa-832a-fa598a11b07f/content>. [in Ukrainian].

10. On the National Guard of Ukraine: Law of Ukraine of 13.03.2014 No. 876-VII. Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada (VVR), 2014, No. 17, p. 594. [in Ukrainian].

11. Matselyk T.O. Functions of executive authorities: some issues / T.O. Matselyk // Scientific Bulletin of the Kyiv National University of Internal Affairs - Kyiv: 2010 - No. 1 - P. 54-60. [in Ukrainian].

12. Koval L.V. Administrative and tort relations / L.V. Koval. - K.: Vyssheshchkola, 1979. - 230 p. [in Ukrainian].

13. Public administration: problems of administrative and legal theory and practice / edited by V.B. Averyanov. K.: Fact, 2003. 384 p. [in Ukrainian].

14. Soroko V. M. Activity of public administration in providing services to Ukrainian society: monograph / V. M. Soroko, A. V. Vyshnevskiy, O. H. Rohozhyn; under the scientific editorship of Candidate of Philosophy Y. A. Pryvalov - Kyiv: NAPA Publishing House, 2007. 180 p. [in Ukrainian].

15. Sokolov A.V. Functions of executive authorities and their features as providers of public services. Public administration: improvement and development № 3, 2014. Internet resource. URL: <http://www.dy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=900>. [in Ukrainian].

16. Zahumenna Y. O. Realization of the law enforcement function of the state by the bodies of internal affairs of Ukraine: Candidate of Law Sciences: 12.00.07 / Y.O. Zahumenna. - K., 2011. 217 p. [in Ukrainian].

17. National Guard of Ukraine as a subject of realization of the law enforcement function of the state: theoretical aspect. Internet resource. URL: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefind-mkaj/https://dspace.univd.edu.ua/server/api/core/bitstreams/b22df0d7-950b-49c2-a7ca-e72a3a391bee/content>. [in Ukrainian].

18. Katrych D.K. Administrative and legal status of the National Police of Ukraine: concept and content. Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University, Series Law. Issue 36. Vol. 2, 2016. pp. 31-35. [in Ukrainian].

19. Administrative activity of the National Police: Study guide / Collective of authors; supervisor of the collective of authors, Candidate of Law, Honored Lawyer of Ukraine V.A. Glukhoveria - Dnipro: Dnipro State University of Internal Affairs, 2017. 248 p. [in Ukrainian].